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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Trifluoro and Hexafluoro Acetylacetonates with Nitrogen Donors

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THE chemistry of metal β -diketonates has aroused recently considerable interest¹ in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extractions^{2,3}, column and thin layer chromatography, N.M.R. shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in polymerisation reactions. Earlier we have reported⁴⁻⁹ many five coordinated nitrogen base adducts of copper(II) and zinc(II) β -diketonates. This communication describes the mixed ligand complexes of the type $M(\text{hfac})_2\text{B}_2$, where $M=\text{Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)}$ and Zn(II) , $M(\text{tfac})_2\text{B}_2$ where $M=\text{Co(II), Ni(II)}$ and $M'(\text{tfac})_2\text{B}$ where $M'=\text{Cu(II)}$ and Zn(II) and B is a nitrogen donor heterocyclic base like quinoline, morpholine and piperidine.

Experimental

Metal β -diketonates were prepared by reported methods⁴⁻⁹.

Methanol solution of metal hexafluoroacetylacetonates were refluxed with the nitrogen bases in (1:2) proportion for thirty minutes and cooled overnight to produce crystalline compounds. Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) trifluoroacetylacetonates were reacted in a similar manner. In case of copper(II) hexafluoroacetylacetonate, benzene was used as a solvent in presence of excess of base. Copper(II) trifluoroacetylacetonate was warmed with excess of the bases in small amount of chloroform to produce a clear solution which on keeping in freeze overnight, gave rise to green crystalline adducts. Analysis and physical measurements were made as reported earlier⁴⁻⁹.

Results and Discussion

The base adducts of cobalt(II) hexafluoro and trifluoroacetylacetonates are pink in colour, nickel(II) complexes light green, copper(II) complexes green and zinc(II) complexes are white crystalline solids. These are soluble in acetone and the molar conductance values are in the range of 6-15 mhos.cm² indicating non-electrolytic nature of these complexes. μ_{eff} values of cobalt(II) complexes are in the range of 4.8-5.2 B. M., those of nickel(II) complexes are in the range of 2.9-3.3 B. M. suggesting octahedral environment of the metal ions. Copper(II) complexes have the moments in the range of 1.76-1.85 B. M.

Infrared spectra of the metal β -diketonates show absorption bands in $\sim 3380-3470$ cm⁻¹ region assignable to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ due to the presence of one or two molecules of coordinated water. In the metal hexafluoroacetylacetonates $\nu(\text{C=O})$ is observed around 1645 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{C=C}) \sim 1615$ cm⁻¹ region. In metal trifluoroacetylacetonates $\nu(\text{C=O})$ is found ~ 1610 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{C=C}) \sim 1580$ cm⁻¹ region. In the far infrared region there are atleast three metal sensitive bands having varying degrees of M-O stretching character because of strong coupling between various vibrational modes. In case of hexafluoroacetylacetonates the least coupled M-O stretching band is observed around 400 cm⁻¹ region and in trifluoroacetylacetonates around 420 cm⁻¹ region. This is quite understandable because presence of electron withdrawing CF₃ group effects the high frequency shift of the carbonyl stretching and low frequency shift of metal-oxygen vibrations compared to the metal acetylacetonates.

In the base adducts $\nu(\text{C=O})$ shifted about 10-15 cm⁻¹ to the high frequency region in case of both hexafluoroacetylacetonates and trifluoroacetylacetonates. The band due to coordinated water also disappeared. Adduct formation has caused a low frequency shift of the M-O stretching band for both the metal- β -diketonates. The magnitude of the shift is about 10-15 cm⁻¹ for nickel(II), cobalt(II) and zinc(II) complexes, but about 30-40 cm⁻¹ for the copper(II). These shifts can be explained in terms of electronic repulsion between a neutral base and hfac or tfac. The general pattern of spectra obtained in the present case is in fair agreement with some earlier observations¹⁰⁻¹². Bonding of the nitrogen ligands have been further substantiated by the observation¹³ of $\nu(\text{M-N})$ in the 280-330 cm⁻¹ region.

In the visible electronic spectra of base adducts of Co(hfac)₂ and Co(tfac)₂, two absorption bands were observed¹⁴ around 18-20 and 8.5 k.k. region attributable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ transitions respectively supporting the octahedral configuration of these complexes. Three absorption bands were observed in case of the base adducts of Ni(hfac)₂ and Ni(tfac)₂ in 9-10, 13-15 and 23-25 k.k. regions assignable to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions respectively indicating the octahedral stereochemistry for these compounds. Cu(hfac)₂ absorbed at 15.4 k.k. ($\epsilon=25$) and the bis adducts gave one broad absorption band in the range of 14.0-14.5 k.k. ($\epsilon=35$) region. Cu(tfac)₂ gave one absorption band at 14.3 k.k. ($\epsilon=30$), which in the mono base adducts was found at 14 k.k. ($\epsilon=70-80$) region. Hence the bis adducts of Cu(hfac)₂ are six-coordinated and the monoadducts of Cu(tfac)₂ are presumably five coordinated^{15,16}.

On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data base adducts of zinc hexafluoroacetylacetonates are six coordinated having octahedral configuration whereas the mono base adducts of zinc

trifluoroacetylacetonates most probably have the penta-coordinated configuration.

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Studies on Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) : Part VI—Copper Mixed-Ligand Complexes Containing Homo Donor Atoms

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MANY copper(II) mixed-ligand complexes containing oxygen and nitrogen as donor atoms were reported in our earlier papers¹⁻⁵. It was found that all such mixed-ligand complexes with hetero donors show marked preference for the formation of

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‡ Abbreviations : en=ethylenediamine, gly=glycinate,
lact=lactate, mal=malonate, ox=oxalate and
pn=1, 3-propylenediamine.

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mixed-ligand complexes over binary complexes. It was considered worthwhile to study mixed-ligand complexes of copper(II) containing only oxygen or only nitrogen as donor atoms to get a better idea of the magnitude of such preferences.

This paper deals with the formation constants of the mixed-ligand complexes formed by copper(II) with (i) ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine and (ii) lactate and oxalate/malonate. The studies were made by spectrophotometry and polarography, results from which may be compared with each other as a check on each other.

The details of the experimental techniques and the method of calculation are the same as given in our earlier^{2, 4} papers.

Results and Discussion

I. Copper-ethylenediamine-1,3-propylenediamine system :

A. *Spectrophotometry* : The method of Newman and Hume⁶ was applied to the determination of the formation constant of $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})]^{2+}$ by spectrophotometry. The value of $\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})}$ obtained is 18.74.

B. *Polarography* : Reversible and diffusion controlled polarographic reductions occurred at moderate concentrations of the two diamines. The $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ values are in the range of 0.030-0.035 V, corresponding to single step reduction involving two electrons.

Effect of pH : Polarograms were recorded each time after the change of pH of the solution containing Cu^{2+} and equal excess of ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is linear in the pH range of 9.3-9.7. The slope of the straight line is 0.053 corresponding to the involvement of two protons at the electrode reaction. The groups which get protonated are the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups, one each of the two diamines, the pK values for which are 9.89 and 10.62 in the case of ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine respectively. The electrode reaction may be represented thus :

The value of overall formation constant of the mixed-ligand complex, $\beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})}$, calculated by the method of Schaap and McMasters⁷, for solutions containing varying concentrations of the two diamines and at different pH values in the range of 9-10, from the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values due to complexation are very nearly constant. The average value of $\log \beta$ is 18.83, comparing very favourably with the value 18.74, from spectrophotometry.